

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Moldova: An Introduction

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The Constitution of the Republic of Moldova states the right of citizens to participate in the administration of public affairs directly, as well as through their representatives. The legal provision on citizens' participation in decision-making is provided by Law 239/2008 on Transparency in the Decision-Making Process. According to Article 6 of the law, citizens, associations established in accordance with the law, other stakeholders have the right to: to participate, under the conditions of this law, in any stage of the decision-making process; to request and obtain information regarding the decision-making process, including to receive the draft decisions accompanied by the related materials, under the conditions of the Law on Access to Information; to propose to the public authorities the initiation of the elaboration and adoption of decisions; to present to the public authorities recommendations regarding the draft decisions under discussion. The public authorities are obliged to take the necessary measures to ensure the possibilities of participation of citizens, of the associations established in accordance with the law, or of other interested parties in the decision-making process.

The National Council for Participation (hereinafter - Council) was created at the initiative of the Government of the Republic of Moldova as an advisory body, without legal status, to ensure the participation of civil society and the private sector in elaboration, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and revision of strategic policy documents. The Council aims to develop and promote a strategic partnership between public authorities, civil society and the private sector in order to strengthen participatory democracy in the Republic of Moldova, by facilitating communication and stakeholder participation in identifying and achieving strategic development priorities at all stages, creating the institutional framework and capacities to ensure the full involvement of stakeholders in the decision-making process. The Council is formed with broad participation of the members of the civil society organizations, 25 in total, representing different domains of interest.

A public consultation mechanism is regulated by Government Decree no 967/2016 and according to internal procedures of public authorities. Information on the decision-making process is provided through general information, for an indefinite general public, and through targeted information, for defined stakeholders. General information implies the obligatory publication of the information on the official web page of the public authority, on the portal www.particip.gov.md, in a space accessible to the public, as well as by dissemination of a press release in central or local media. Public authorities initiate a public consultation to inform and receive recommendations from stakeholders. These consultations could be organized in different forms that may be in form of soliciting the opinions of civil society, experts,

professional associates, academia; setting up permanent or ad hoc working groups; organizing public debates; conducting public hearings; conducting public surveys etc.

Despite the legal framework in Moldova provides for an extensive set of opportunities, yet, implementation is far from satisfactory. Many citizens show indifference to political participation while others lack the knowledge needed to set democratic processes in motion. Given the poor economic situation in the country, specifically in the rural areas, the level of economic development is very limited. A significant part of the active members of the local community left for a better life abroad, which further hindered popular participation in local decision-making. Additionally, the strong legacy of repressive institutions continues to discourage citizen activism and open consultation.

Moldova's State Chancellery Report¹⁸ on transparency in the decision-making process finds that the legislative framework lacks a methodology on the consultation process, the web portal <www.particip.gov.md> is not well structured, and that additional legal instruments are needed to help contesting the actions of public authorities in case of non-compliance with the law, while the format of the National Council for Participation could be reviewed to ensure greater transparency and representativeness of the associative sector in cooperation with the central public administration. At the local level the situation is even more challenging. While there is a register of the acts of local public authorities (LPAs), the platform <www.actelocale.md> publishes the final and approved decisions only, not the drafts or other accompanying documents which could facilitate the participation of civil society organizations and their constituents in the decision-making process. At the same time, not all LPAs publish their decisions on the mentioned web page.

A recent study on the involvement of citizens in the life of their communities¹⁹ revealed the following reality: '85% of the population did not participate at all in any meeting of local councils in the locality (although, according to the law, local council meetings are public); It should be noted that the vast majority of the population (91%) did not write a complaint about a local problem; 79% stated that they had not contacted any local, district, deputy or minister elected in the last twelve months; therefore, we can emphasize the absence of any communication with the elected representatives of the people/state representatives. Only 7% of respondents contacted at least one media institution to report a local issue to. Survey participants do not frequently use social media networks as a tool to discuss a community problem. In the last year, 91% of respondents did not make any posts about any issue to them in the community.'

From these findings one may argue that citizens have limited confidence that local authorities will be able to solve community problems. At the same time, the data indicates also a state of

¹⁸ State Chancellery of Moldova, 'Privind asigurarea transparenței în procesul decizional de către autoritățile administrației publice centrale' (Report, 2019).

¹⁹ Doru Petruți, Viorelia Zaharco and Alexandru Crivițchi, 'implicarea cetățenilor în viața comunităților' (imas 2018) <<http://imas.md/pic/archives/12/implicarea%20cetatenilor%20in%20viata%20comunitatilor.pdf>>.

indifference of the population or ignorance of civic involvement tools. It could be also concluded that existing civil involvement institutional framework is still burdensome for an ordinary citizen and may require further improvement.

The real total number of active civil society organizations (CSOs) in the Republic of Moldova is not known. Most registered CSOs (about 65 per cent) are located in Chisinau, although this territorial-administrative unit represents only about 25 per cent of the total population of the country. According to some studies, only about 25 per cent of the total number of CSOs are sufficiently active and develop various projects and initiatives, and among the causes is both the inadequacy of funding within the country and the lack of revenue generation mechanisms through services.

Civil society development is one of the concerns of the political class in Moldova. For the period 2018-2020 Parliament has approved a strategy with a goal to contribute to the development of the civil society that substitutes a similar strategy approved for the period 2012-2015.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, 1994

Law no 239/2008 on Transparency in Decision-Making

Law no 51/2018 on the Approval of the Development Strategy of Civil Society for the Period 2018–2020 <https://www.legis.md/cautare/getResults?doc_id=105436&lang=ro>

Government Decree no 11/2010 on the Creation of the National Council for Participation

Government Decree no 967/2016 on the Mechanism of Public Consultation with Civil Society in the Decision-Making Process

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